

Dynamics of quality of life in monotherapy of some anticonvulsants in patients with epilepsy: comparative analysis

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Abstract. Epilepsy is a chronic disease that leads to various social and psychological consequences. Due to impact of epilepsy on the psychosocial status of patients, contributing to the formation of perception of their position in life, epilepsy is characterized by reduced quality of life. With purpose to evaluate the quality of life of epilepsy patients with estimating its dynamics on the background of monotherapy with some antiepileptic drugs studied 102 patients aged of 18-44 years. Using the methodology for assessing the quality of life of patients with epilepsy using QOLIE -31 questionnaire along with clinical, instrumental methods of examination is a reliable criterion for evaluating the additional efficacy and tolerability of therapy. To achieve a sufficient amount of research in this field, such studies requires further development , as it is a signal for physicians about available fears of patients and informs patients about the problems typical to their disease, facilitate interaction between physician and patient about the decision concerning tactics of diagnosis and treatment.

Key words: epilepsy, quality of life, anticonvulsants.

1. Introduction

One of the chronic neurological diseases leading to various social and psychological consequences is epilepsy, it is potentially curable, remission can be achieved in a relatively large number of patients. Adequate therapy improves health and social prognosis, enables each patient to realize their potential. In connection with the influence of epilepsy on the psychosocial status of patients, contributing to the formation of the perception of their life position, epilepsy is characterized by a decrease in the quality of life. The quality of life of patients with epilepsy is lower than in the general population [3,4,5,11]. In the United States and many countries of Western Europe and CIS countries, studies of the quality of life of patients with epilepsy were conducted [14,17]. It was revealed that the risk factors for the quality of life are the frequency of seizures, work capacity and concomitant mental disorders (QOLIE-31 total score questionnaire) [8]. In addition, a low level of education, a high frequency of seizures, and a long history of epilepsy were predictors of lower scores [9,10]. In Russia, the indicators of the total QOLIE-31 score in patients with epilepsy were quite low [14]. Although the two countries may have cultural differences, in most studies, the frequency of seizures is the most important indicator of quality of life [12,13,15]. At present, the relevance of continuing research in this direction in the Republic of Uzbekistan is undeniable.

The purpose of this paper is to evaluate the dynamics of the quality of life of patients with epilepsy on the background of monotherapy with certain anticonvulsants.

2. Materials and methods

The study included 102 patients aged 18-44 years (mean age 30.2 ± 12.3 years): 57 men and 45 women. All patients underwent complete standard clinical, neurological and electroencephalographic studies. In addition, all patients completed the QOLIE-31 questionnaire before and after optimizing antiepileptic therapy (since this is the most informative method for assessing the quality of life of patients with epilepsy) [2,7]. The questionnaire consists of 31 questions grouped into seven sub-scales that assess questions such as "Fear of attack", "General quality of life", "Emotional well-being", "Energy/fatigue", "Cognitive functioning", "Effect of antiepileptic preparations" and "Social functioning". The overall score was also determined. According to the seven main parameters of the questionnaire, a generalized index was calculated, which is a weighted linear combination of these main parameters. The weights required to build a generalized indicator were proposed by the authors of the questionnaire [2,3,17]. The results obtained were converted into scores from 0 to 100, with higher values reflecting a higher quality of life.

At the first visit, anticonvulsants were prescribed or adjusted in accordance with modern clinical guidelines and standards for managing patients with epilepsy [6,16]. Titration of the antiepileptic drug (AED) was carried out taking into account the nature of seizures and the epileptic syndrome, the effectiveness of previous therapy, as well as interactions with other drugs taken by patients [1,6]. The analysis of the results was carried out at the following control points: 1) before the start of antiepileptic therapy or its correction, 2) 4 months after the start or optimization of therapy. The analysis of the results was carried out on a standard IBM-compatible computer with data processing by groups using Excell-2007 and Graph Pad Software. Statistical comparison of mean values in groups was performed using Student's t-test.

3. Results and discussion

The clinical picture of the disease was represented by the following types of seizures: simple partial (PP) — 27.5% (n=28), complex partial (automatisms) (SR) — 19.5% (n=20), a large group of patients were observed for the second time -generalized seizures (HCV) - 53% (n=54). Of all cases, 35.3% of epilepsies were idiopathic (n=36), 54% symptomatic (n=55) and 10.7% cryptogenic (n=11). According to ILAE recommendations in 1995, symptomatic epilepsy was remote.

in 58 (57%) patients (of which 19% had a stroke, 31% - infection, 50% - trauma) and progressive in 44 (43%) patients (58% - intracranial formation, 42% - degenerative).

Increased fatigue, decreased active attention and mental performance occurred with approximately the same frequency in both symptomatic and idiopathic epilepsy, while this indicator was lower in symptomatic partial epilepsy. Memory loss was found in all forms of epilepsy with a significant decrease with a predominance of a short-term component in symptomatic generalized epilepsy and a permanent component in symptomatic partial epilepsy.

We also compared patients with long-term remission of seizures without epileptiform activity (n=52) and patients with a remission period of more than 1 year and the absence of epileptiform activity detected on routine EEG (n=35). It was found that patients who had a remission period of 2 to 1 year without epileptiform activity on the EEG (n=42) had better test results compared to patients in whom the remission period was less than 1 year and was combined with the registration of epileptiform activity on the EEG. EEG (n=27). At the same time, in patients with long-term remission and receiving longer basic therapy (n=12), worse results were recorded in the study of attention and memory processes.

All patients with epilepsy were on monotherapy and received the following antiepileptic drugs: carbamazepine - 37% (n=25), valproate - 37% (n=23), topiramate - 15% (n=26), lamotrigine - 11% (n=28).

The effectiveness of AEDs in this study was assessed by the reduction or complete regression of seizures, the absence of side effects, as well as the dynamics of changes in the quality of life of patients. The complete absence of seizures was regarded as 100% pharmacological remission. Therapy was considered effective when the frequency of seizures was reduced by 50% or more, ineffective

when the frequency of seizures was reduced by less than 50% [4,6]. The dynamics of intellectual and mental disorders in patients with epilepsy on the background of monotherapy with various drugs is the subject of another review of our study.

An analysis of the frequency of seizures in patients receiving carbamazepine at a dose of 800-1600 mg at the first visit a month after the start of therapy showed that the absence of seizures was noted in 53% of cases, in 26% the treatment was effective, and in 21% the treatment was ineffective. But during the follow-up at the second visit, 68% of seizures regressed, in 32% of patients the therapy was effective. In dynamics, the number of patients with complete regression of seizures increased, which is associated with a longer period of dynamic observation (Fig. 1).

In the group of patients treated with valproate (1000-3000 mg Depakine chrono) (n=19), at the second visit regression was achieved in 79% (n=15), in 16% (n=3) the therapy was effective. In 5% (n=1) of patients, the frequency of attacks decreased by less than 50%, for them the dose was increased to 20 mg/kg of body weight. During the observation period, the number of patients with complete regression of seizures increased, which indicates the effectiveness of the therapy. The clinical picture of the disease was represented by the following types of seizures: simple partial seizures - 26%, complex partial (automatisms) - 32%, a large group consisted of patients with secondary generalized seizures - 42%.

Figure 1. The effectiveness of monotherapy in the study groups.

In the group treated with topiramate at a dose of 200-400 mg at the second visit, complete regression of seizures was achieved in 33%, in 47% the seizures decreased by 50%, in 20% there was a decrease in the frequency of seizures by less than 50%, which is associated with a slow titrating the dose of the drug. After further dose adjustment for 6 months, topiramate was highly effective - remission was achieved in 60%, in the remaining 40% of patients, seizures decreased by more than 50%.

In groups where patients received therapy with Lamotrigine for 4 months, 33% of patients achieved a complete remission of seizures, in 67% of the seizures decreased by more than 50%. Subsequently, these figures were 67% and 33%, respectively.

Analysis of QoL according to the QOLIE-31 questionnaire and some other scales showed that AED therapy improved significantly, changes in other indicators did not reach significance.

Therapy with Carbamazepine showed a significant improvement in the quality of life on the scales - "Fear of seizures", "General HD", "Emotional well-being", "Energy/fatigue" ($p < 0.05$), indicators "Cognitive well-being", "functioning" was close to statistical significance ($p = 0.05$). There were no significant changes on the scales "Effect of antiepileptic drugs" and "Social functioning".

When analyzing the data, patients treated with valproate initially had a low quality of life, especially in terms of "Fear of seizures", "General HD", "Emotional well-being". A re-examination of patients treated with Depakine Chrono showed a significant improvement only in terms of "Fear of seizures", "General BD", "Cognitive functioning", "Effect of antiepileptic drugs", "Social functioning"

($p < 0.05$). Changes on the scale "Emotional well-being", "Energy/fatigue" were unreliable ($p > 0.05$), which indicates the absence of their influence on the emotional background of patients. In patients treated with valproate, the quality of life indicators were higher than in patients treated with carbamazepine, the therapy was effective, and according to EEG data, significantly better results were obtained.

Comparison of the outcomes of the QOL indicator in different groups (Fig. 2) showed that the largest number of observed patients in the groups treated with lamotrigine rated their quality of life as high (80%), in the topiramate groups - (75%), Depakine - (70%). In patients treated with carbamazepine, this indicator was adequate to good QoL (40%). When taking Depakine, Topiramate, Lamotrigine, these figures were 30%, 20%, 16%, respectively.

Significantly better QoL was shown by patients treated with Depakine Chrono, whose anticonvulsant efficacy was second after Lamotrigine.

Figure 2. Analysis of the dynamics of the quality of life against the background of monotherapy in the treatment groups.

The overall frequency of side effects was low, comparable to those of topiramate, but their severity was insignificant and did not lead to drug withdrawal. The levels of the subscales "Cognitive functioning", "Effect of antiepileptic drugs", "Social functioning" passed without a decrease in patients receiving lamotrigine and depakine.

Thus, patients who received valproate, lamotrigine and topiramate rated their quality of life higher, which is undoubtedly due to its high efficacy and good tolerability. The results of a comparative assessment of the overall QOL of the groups presented in Figure 1, and the data obtained from the analysis of QoL depending on the therapeutic effect, indicate a significant effectiveness of therapy in relation to the QOL of patients with epilepsy and the reduction of seizures is important. factor of it. When analyzing the quality of life of patients and depending on the type of seizure, a significantly lower quality of life was obtained in patients with CPR $p < 0.01$. To a lesser extent, the QOL of SHSP decreased ($p < 0.05$). There were no statistically significant differences in the groups of patients with SPT and remission of the disease. The strong correlation of QoL from the effect of therapy ($r > 0.70$) in patients treated with valproate (Depakine) is explained by better tolerability of the drug.

In all groups, on the background of therapy, seizures decreased or completely regressed. When assessing the quality of life before treatment, it showed that it was the same in all groups; after 4 months of therapy, it was found that higher scores on all subscales of the questionnaire were observed in patients who received Depakine Chrono and Lamotrigine. Significantly lower scores on QOL scales were observed in patients who had side effects during therapy with carbamazepine and topiramate ($p < 0.05$).

Thus, a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of AEDs on the quality of life of patients with epilepsy showed higher rates in patients receiving valproate and lamotrigine, which correlates with higher efficacy and tolerability of therapy ($r=0.55$). Topiramate showed the highest anticonvulsant efficacy among all groups of drugs, the frequency of clinically significant side effects and a negative impact on the quality of life during use was not observed, which does not distinguish it from valproate. The degree of change on the subscales "Emotional well-being", "Cognitive functioning" during treatment with carbamazepine was significantly higher ($p<0.05$) than in patients treated with lamotrigine and valproate ($p<0.01$). This confirms the data available in the literature on a greater negative effect of topiramate on cognitive functions than other antiepileptic drugs [13,15].

The overall QoL in patients treated with topiramate was assessed as good, however, in absolute terms, it was closer to the estimates of the groups of patients treated with valproate (high QoL) than to the estimates of patients treated with carbamazepine (good QoL). Significantly better QoL was in patients treated with lamotrigine, whose anticonvulsant efficacy was slightly lower only after topiramate. The overall frequency of side effects was the lowest for lamotrigine and valproate, comparable to those for topiramate, but their severity was insignificant and did not lead to drug withdrawal. The intensity of changes on the subscales "Cognitive functioning" does not go beyond subclinical disorders.

4. Conclusions

In all monotherapy groups, seizures decreased or completely regressed. Assessment of the quality of life before treatment showed that it was the same in all groups. Among all the studied groups of AEDs, the most pronounced antiparoxysmal effect was found in valproate. When treated with antiepileptic drugs, the greatest impact on the individual subscale and total QoL score was found in patients diagnosed with valproate or lamotrigine monotherapy; in other groups of patients, QoL was lower. Thus, optimized pharmacotherapy reduces the frequency of side effects, increases efficiency and improves the emotional, psychological and physical condition of patients [16]. Seizure remission is not enough to achieve high QoL, as the quality of life is affected by the presence or absence of side effects, psycho-emotional disorders, and social adaptation of patients [19]. The use of the methodology for assessing the quality of life of patients with epilepsy using the QOLIE-31 questionnaire, along with clinical, instrumental methods of examination, is a reliable criterion for assessing the additional efficacy and tolerability of therapy. To achieve a sufficient amount of research in this area, such studies require further development, as they are a signal to doctors about the patient's fears and inform patients about the problems specific to their disease, facilitate the interaction between the doctor and the patient regarding the decision-making regarding the tactics of diagnosis and treatment.

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